

Effect of Biofertilizers (Rabbit Urine and Neem Cake) on Agromorphological Parameters of Okra (*Abelmoschus Esculentus*) in the Far North of Cameroon

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
25 June 2025

ABSTRACT

In Cameroon, food security is threatened by increasing population growth, declining land fertility, and rising chemical fertilizer prices. It is becoming imperative to seek other sources of nutrients that can contribute to food security in a sustainable manner. The objective of this study is to improve okra productivity using biofertilizers (rabbit urine and neem cake) as an alternative to chemical fertilization. The study was conducted using a Fisher block design, including three replicates. A single factor was studied, with the biofertilizers comprising three modalities: a control (T0) without fertilizer, treatment (T1) consisting of rabbit urine applied at 10 L per experimental unit, or 0.5 L/plant, and treatment (T2) consisting of neem cake applied at 3 kg per experimental unit, or 150 g/plant. Growth and yield parameters were evaluated. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using Genstat 12 edition software at a significance level of 5 %. The results show that with neem cake, plants have the best height (39.87 cm), the highest number of leaves (9 leaves) and the best collar diameter (12.89 mm) at 49 DAS. The rabbit urine treatment shows the precocity to floral induction (44 DAS) and flowering (47 DAS). The best yield in average number of fruits (20,000 fruits/ha) and average fruit weight (4.08 t/ha) is obtained with neem cake, followed by rabbit urine with 20,000 fruits/ha and an average fruit weight of 3.55 t/ha. The lowest yield (12,000 fruits/ha) and average fruit weight (1.19 t/ha) is obtained with the control. Neem cake is the biofertilizer that helps to further improve okra productivity.

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KEYWORDS: biofertilizer, rabbit urine, neem cake, okra, Far North Cameroon.

1. INTRODUCTION

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*) is an annual plant of the Malvaceae family, cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions (Kouayet et al., 2021). All parts of the plant are valued for food, medicinal purposes, artisanally, and even industrially (Sanouna et al., 2020 ; Siemonsma and Hamon, 2004 ; Marius et al., 1997). Global okra production is estimated at nearly 6 million tonnes per year, with India as the world's largest producer (FAO, 2021). West and Central Africa accounts for about 10 % of global production (FAO, 2019). Cameroonian production is estimated at around 120,000 tonnes per year (FAO, 2021). This production is mainly intended for domestic consumption, but a tiny amount is exported to neighboring countries. Although the consumption of okra fruits and leaves is growing significantly in response to strong national and regional demand, the average okra production in Cameroon is about 2.6 t/ha,

contrary to the expected yield of between 12 and 15 t/ha (FAO, 2019). In terms of human nutrition, okra is rich in vitamins, minerals, and fiber (Shamsul and Arifuzzaman, 2007). Karakoltsidis and Constantinides (1975) showed that dry okra seeds are an interesting source of lipids (20 %) and proteins (20 %). Despite this potential, the demand for okra and its by-products far exceeds supply (FAO, 2019). Reducing crop yields is one of the major problems facing sub-Saharan Africa. Declining soil fertility is recognized as one of the main causes of this situation (Kaho et al., 2007; Kaho et al., 2011). Cameroon is no exception. Thus, in order to improve soil fertility to boost crop yields, farmers are using synthetic chemicals as soil fertility factors (Galani et al., 2018; Mondjeli et al., 2015). Although the effects of mineral fertilizers are immediate, they nevertheless present risks for human and animal health, soil acidification, soil depletion, reduction of wildlife, reduction of organic matter content and

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cation exchange capacity of soils (WHO, 2023; Galani et al., 2018). Also the high prices of chemical fertilizers are a luxury that many farmers cannot afford (Traore et al., 2019 ; Tchingio, 2023 ; Bayanbe, 2023). These risks have led many producers to limit the use of chemicals and to recycle livestock products in order to ensure more environmentally friendly production (Zimmerer and De Hannn, 2017). Livestock farming in general and that of rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) in particular is increasingly growing in Cameroon due to the prized quality of its white meat. As a consequence, there is an abundant production of waste from this livestock. The use of human urine and feces for agricultural production has been widely practiced in many parts of the world (Anna et al., 2011 ; Kirchmann and Petterson, 1995 ; Hanan, 2004). The use of rabbit urine is not left out, especially since the breeding of this monogastric is clearly expanding. Kirchmann and Petterson (1995) are showed that urine is a high-quality and low-cost organic fertilization alternative compared to chemical fertilizers. Similarly, (Temgoua, 2017; Takuete, 2012; Robert et al., 2011) justify the use of urine in agriculture in the sense that urine contains essential nutrients such as nitrogen, potassium and phosphates necessary for plant growth. In addition, the nitrogen level in urine is high because their main food preference is fodder and they drink little water (Mutai, 2020). Information regarding the fertilizing effect of rabbit urine compared to chemical fertilizers on okra yields has not yet been studied. Thus, recycling rabbit urine for use in okra cultivation may be an effective palliative to address soil fertility problems, in the face of calls for organic production (Amoabeng et al., 2013). Also in the reforestation process of the northern zone of Cameroon, thousands of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) trees have been planted. It is then that neem cake, which is a product resulting from the extraction of oil from neem seeds, is used in agriculture to improve agricultural productivity and soil fertility (Oyinlola et al., 2017; Folefack et al., 2012).

Studies conducted on the evolution of soil fertility in the far north of Cameroon (Guyotte et al., 1997; M'biandoun and Douzet, 2000), have highlighted the declines in soil nitrogen levels and the insufficiency of available phosphorus (Boli, 1996). Thus, to compensate for excessive exports by crops and maintain good productivity, agricultural practices must move towards sustainable and low-cost cropping systems involving biofertilization and organic fertilization practices. This study will examine the effect of rabbit urine and neem cake on okra growth and yield parameters in order to improve soil health and ensure nutrient replenishment, while preserving the environment to ensure food security.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Presentation of the study site

The trial was conducted at the Maroua Regional College of Agriculture (CRA) farm, located in the Djarengol Delegue neighborhood in the Maroua 1 Council Subdivision. This farm is located at 10°58'68.6" North latitude and 14°30'24.8" East longitude, and at an altitude of 402 m. The climate is dry Sudano-Sahelian, characterized by a long dry season lasting approximately 7 months (October to May) and a short rainy season lasting 3 to 5 months (June to October). The average annual rainfall varies between 600 and 800 mm and the temperature between 17 °C and 42 °C with an average of 34 °C (Brabant and Gavaud, 1985; Djoufack et al., 2012). The site soil is sandy-clayey (Seiny, 1990 ; M'biandoun and Olina, 2007).

2.2. Plant Material

The plant material used is a local variety of okra grown in the Far North of Cameroon (Figure 1). This local variety of okra is adapted to the environment ; its cycle lasts between 60 and 65 days. It is easy to store and is highly appreciated by producers and consumers.

Figure 1: Seeds of the local okra variety used

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2.3. Organic Fertilizers

Two organic fertilizers were used in this trial: rabbit urine obtained from the NGO PADK (Powerful Action for the Development of Kadey) in Ngotto, Kadey (Eastern

Cameroon) and neem almond cake obtained from a cooperative producing non-timber forest products in Maroua, which extracts and markets neem oil. The biofertilizers used and their doses are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Treatments and their doses per hectare

Treatment Code	Fertilizers	Doses/EU	Doses/ha
T0	Control	0	0
T1 (RU)	Rabbit Urine	10L/EU	16,666.67 L
T2 (NC)	Neem Cake	3 kg/EU	5000 kg

T0: Without fertilizer T1: Rabbit Urine (RU) T2: Neem Cake (NC)

2.4. Experimental Design

The experimental design is a Fisher block design comprising three treatments: the control (T0) without fertilizer, rabbit urine (RU), and neem cake (NC), repeated three times. The experimental unit consists of 4 rows comprising 5 pockets each. The spacing between rows is 0.8 m and 0.5 m between plants in the row. The experimental unit is an area of 6 m². The distance between blocks is 1 m and 0.5 m between experimental units, giving a total area of 80 m².

2.5. Conduct of the trial

Plot preparation began with clearing, followed by cleaning. This was followed by manual plowing. Staking was carried out on February 24, 2024. Sowing took place on March 1, 2024 at a rate of 2 to 3 seeds per pocket, at a depth of approximately 3 to 5 cm. Each experimental unit had approximately 60 plants before thinning, then 20 plants after thinning, for a total of 180 plants across the entire experimental unit. Watering was done every two days by gravity through irrigation channels from a submerged pump borehole located on the site. The plot was regularly cleared of weeds by hand weeding with hoes. A cover crop treatment was provided against pests from the beginning of floral initiation until the end of fruiting, using neem oil (biopesticide) every two weeks at a dose of one liter per hectare. The biofertilizer treatments consisted of a control T0 without fertilizer, a single dose of rabbit urine T1 = 10 L/EU, or 0.5 L/plant and corresponding to 16,666.67 L/ha and a single dose of neem cake T2 = 3 kg/EU, or 150 g per plant corresponding to 5000 kg/ha. The neem cake was applied two weeks before sowing as a base fertilizer (5 t/ha). The rabbit urine was spread evenly around each pocket with a plant, at the start (19 DAS) and one week before flower induction (33 DAS) as a top dressing fertilizer. The first harvest was carried out 55 DAS in the fresh state and the following harvests every four days manually using a knife. Once harvested, the fruits were weighed.

2.6. Measured parameters

The quantitative and qualitative traits are studied. They were described according to the okra descriptor (Charrier, 1983). Data were collected from six central plants, excluding the border lines of each experimental unit, using the method described by Mustefa (2014).

- ✓ Plant height was determined using a tape measure graduated in meters from the plant collar to the apex from 29 DAS, 39 DAS, and 49 DAS ;
- ✓ The collar diameter was measured at the plant collar using a digital caliper graduated in millimeters from 29 DAS, 39 DAS, and 49 DAS ;
- ✓ The number of leaf (NL) was determined by manually counting on each leaves of the six plants from 29 DAS, 39 DAS, and 49 DAS ;
- ✓ For floral induction and flowering, they were determined after visual observation and consisted of counting the number of days after sowing that flower buds and flowers appeared respectively ;
- ✓ The number of fruits was obtained by manually counting the ripe fruits on six plants in each experimental unit ;
- ✓ The fruit weight was obtained by weighing using an ACCULAB GS 200 electronic balance with a sensitivity of 0.001 g. This is the cumulative weight of ripe fruits obtained on six plants in each experimental unit.

2.7. Data Analysis

The data were entered and formatted using Microsoft Office Excel 2013. The analyses were performed using GenStat statistical package 12 edition software at the 5 % significance level. When a significant difference was noted between treatments for a given trait, the ANOVA was supplemented with the DUNCAN test. This test made it possible to identify homogeneous groups (Dagnelie, 1998 and 2012).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Effect of biofertilizers on growth parameters

Table 2 shows the mean plant heights that vary across treatments and time. At 29 DAS, plant heights ranged from 9.76 cm (T0) to 13.71 cm (T2) ; at 39 DAS, they ranged from 18.37 cm (T0) to 29.37 cm (T2) ; and at 49 DAS, they ranged from 28.16 cm (T0) to 39.87 cm (T2). The lowest heights were obtained with the control (T0), while the highest heights were obtained with the neem cake (T2) and rabbit urine (T1) treatments. Analyses of variance showed that at 29 DAS, 39 DAS, and 49 DAS, there was a highly significant difference ($p < 0.001$) between treatments suggesting variation among treatments. The better performance observed with neem cake could be explained by their richness in organic matter, notably nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium ; since nitrogen promotes the vegetative development of plants, cell multiplication and allows the elongation of stems and leaves (Lima et al., 2009 ; Rahman, 2013 ; Faisal et al., 2017) ; in addition, the combined richness in phosphorus and potassium of neem cake stimulates the plant's overall resistance and helps develop its rooting system which is favorable for the rapid transport of nutrients ; this promotes rapid plant development (Marschner, 1995; Dabre et al., 2017). The availability of mineral elements in neem cake could also be explained by rapid mineralization thanks to the action of microorganisms and the assimilation of mineral elements by plants, unlike rabbit urine (Calvet and Villemin, 1996; Cobo et al., 2002). These results corroborate those of Garba and Oyinlola (2014) and Oyinlola et al. (2014) who observed that neem cake promotes rapid crop growth by increasing the availability of micro and macronutrients. The poor plant performance obtained on control plots could be explained by the fact that they received no amendments throughout the crop cycle.

As for the evolution of the average number of leaves (Table 2), at 29 DAS we observe that there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the treatments, which vary between 5 leaves with the control treatment (T0) and 6 leaves with the neem cake (T2) and rabbit urine (T1) treatments. At 39 DAS and 49 DAS, the analyses of variance show that there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the treatments. The low variation observed between the treatments at 29 DAS, 39 DAS and 49 DAS would be due to the genotypic expression of the okra variety used (Kœchlin., 1989). It should be noted that on the vegetative level, the local variety of okra used presents a certain homogeneity on the vegetative level. There would be a genetically predefined limit number of leaves around which the average obtained by the variety used is located.

The evolution of the collar diameter (Table 2) as a function of time shows that at 29 DAS, there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the treatments, which vary between 4.51 mm with the control treatment (T0) and 5.58 mm with the

neem cake treatment (T2). At 39 DAS and 49 DAS, analyses of variance show that there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the treatments. At 39 DAS, the collar diameter varies between 6.44 mm with the control (T0) and 11.62 mm with the neem cake treatment (T2). At 49 DAS, the collar diameter varies between 8.03 mm with the control (T0) and 12.89 mm with the neem cake treatment (T2). It is observed that at the end of the cycle, the collar diameters differ depending on the treatments. The difference observed between plants at 39 DAS and 49 DAS would be due to the nature and physicochemical quality of the organic fertilizers used (Duprarque, 2011). In fact, according to Calvet and Villemin (1996), when the mineralization of organic matter is complete, the availability of minerals for plants is ensured. Neem cake is recognized for its significant contribution of organic matter and essential nutrients. Several authors (Hunsigi, 2001 ; Joshi and Prabhakara 2005 ; Ramanathan 2006 and Traore et al., 2019) have also indicated significant N, P and K contents in neem cake capable of improving plant nutrition. These observations contrast with those of Yakouba et al., (2022) who revealed that compost and poultry droppings are more effective biofertilizers than neem cake and cow dung for cotton cultivation in the Far North of Cameroon. The difference between these amendments could be explained by their nature and physicochemical quality indeed. When a biofertilizer is not well decomposed, its assimilation takes time because it must undergo the complete mineralization process and consequently, the release of mineral elements and their availability for crops is slow. Cobo et al. (2002) showed in this regard that the rate of decomposition of organic matter and the increase in production are closely linked to the synchronization between the release of nutrients and their assimilation by plants. The poor growth of okra on control plots (T0) could be attributed to the removal by previous crops without replacement of mineral elements from the soil. Several tropical soils show problems of mineral element deficiency and reduced yield just after a short cultivation period. These results corroborate those of Traore et al., (2015) and Da (2019) who showed that most soils cultivated for many years without a real strategy to maintain or improve their fertility, lose their mineral element content and other chemical parameters over the years. Ray et al., 2020 showed in this regard that plants need nutrients for their growth, the majority of which are extracted from the soil through the work of microorganisms. The plots that received urine, unlike the control plots suggest the effectiveness of the stimulation of plant growth by urine (Akpam-Idiok, 2012). Neem cake contributes to further improving plant growth by optimizing soil fertility through the action of the microorganisms it contains. It is an excellent source of nutrients providing essential macronutrients for plant growth (Garba et Oyinlola, 2014 ; Oyinlola et al., 2014).

Table 2: Effect of biofertilizers on okra plant height, number of leaves and coller diameter

Traitements	Plants height (cm)			Number of leaves			Coller diameter (mm)		
	PH (29DAS)	PH (39DAS)	PH (49DAS)	NL (29DAS)	NL (39DAS)	NL (49DAS)	DC (29DAS)	DC (39DAS)	DC (49DAS)
T0	9,76 ±0,83 ^a	18,37±1,92 ^a	28,16±1,51 ^a	5±0 ^a	7±0,57 ^a	8±0,57 ^a	4,51±0,94 ^a	6,44±0,71 ^a	8,03±0,26 ^a
T1 (RU)	12,17±0,21 ^b	20,71±1,23 ^b	31,3±1,06 ^b	6±1,0 ^b	8±0,57 ^a	8±0,57 ^a	5,04±0,36 ^a	7,29±1,20 ^a	9,27±0,59 ^b
T2 (NC)	13,71±1,41 ^b	29,37±0,71 ^c	39,87±1,74 ^c	6±0,57 ^b	7±1,0 ^a	9±1,0 ^a	5,58±0,84 ^a	11,62±0,21 ^b	12,89±0,74 ^c

T0: Without fertilizer ; T1: Rabbit Urine (RU) ; T2: Neem Cake (NC) ; PH: Plant Height ; NL: Number of Leaves ; CD: Coller Diameter

3.2 Effect of biofertilizers on plant phenological parameters.

Table 3 shows the dates of floral induction and flowering according to the treatments. The first floral induction appeared at 44 DAS with the rabbit urine treatment (T1) ; followed by the neem cake treatment (T2) at 47 DAS, then the control treatment (T0) at 48 DAS. In contrast, the first flowering began at 47 DAS with the rabbit urine treatment (T1) ; followed by the neem cake treatment (T2) at 50 DAS, then the control treatment (T0) at 52 DAS. Analyses of variance revealed significant differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$). The observed variations suggest heterogeneity between treatments The local okra variety used would be

early, because the results obtained corroborate with those of Sawadogo et al. (2010) who showed that varieties whose flowering occurs between 45 and 50 DAS are said to have a very early cycle. However, floral induction, like flowering, would not necessarily be linked to the genetic makeup of the variety used, as Rabiou et al. (2022) pointed out ; but also the contributions of biofertilizers could interact. The treatment with rabbit urine would stimulate precocity in the okra variety used. This is explained by the release of mineral elements after the mineralization of the rabbit urine during the 2nd spreading at 33 DAS, and which would be immediately assimilated by the plants; unlike the neem cake which was applied only once, two weeks before sowing (March 1, 2024).

Table 3: Effect of biofertilizers on floral induction, flowering, and yields components

Treatments	Floral induction (DAS)	Flowering (DAS)	Number of fruits (ha)	Weight of fruits (t/ha)
T0	48±0.58	52±1,0	12,000±0.58	1.19±5.0
T1 (RU)	44±1.00	47±1.0	20,000±0.58	3.55±9.01
T2 (NC)	47±1.00	50±1.0	20,000±0.58	4.08±3.82

T0: Without fertilizer T1: Rabbit Urine (RU) T2: Neem Cake (NC) DAS: Day After Sowing

3.3. Effects of Biofertilizers on yield parameters

Table 3 shows the number of okra fruits harvested and their weights. Thus, the average number of fruits per hectare varies from 12,000 fruits/ha with the control (T0) to 20,000 fruits/ha with the rabbit urine (T1) and neem cake (T2) treatments. Similarly, fruit weight varies from 1.19 t/ha with the control (T0), followed by the rabbit urine (T1) treatment with 3.55 t/ha ; then neem cake treatment (T2) with 4.08 t/ha. Analyses of variance revealed significant differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$). These results corroborate with those of Traore et al. (2019) who obtained in the South Sudanese zone of Burkina Faso, an increase in corn grain yield with the use of neem cake. Similarly, Oyinola et al. (2017) in Nigeria have achieved better yields on tomato cultivation with neem cake. Aderni (2006) and Azim et al. (2011) revealed that when used as an amendment, neem cake not only enriches the soil with

organic matter and nutrients, but also decreases nitrogen losses by inhibiting nitrification (Lokanadhan et al., 2012). The increase in the number of fruits and their masses shows that treatments with neem cake (NC), and rabbit urine (RU) contribute to the improvement of okra yields, compared to the control (T0). This is explained by the presence of mineral elements easily assimilated by plants in neem cake and rabbit urine. Indeed, the evolution of the transformation of biofertilizers depends strongly on the activity of microorganisms. (Iqbal et al., 2014; Meliani et al., 2017) have indeed shown that microorganisms are beneficial for soils and plants in the sense that they play a dynamic role through the degradation of organic matter, contributing to the maintenance of soil fertility and also to the improvement of agricultural yields. These results corroborate those of Li et al. (2012) and Khalid et al. (2014) who reported that the use of

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biofertilizers improves soil fertility. The low yield obtained on the control plot reflects the poor nature of the soils, due to the removal of previous crops without replacement of mineral elements. Several tropical soils suffered from problems of mineral element deficiency and yield decline immediately after a crop. Kaho et al. (2007) revealed that this situation not only predisposes the soil to erosion, but also leads to rapid depletion of mineral elements, particularly nitrogen and phosphorus.

4. CONCLUSION

This work shows that neem cake and rabbit urine used as biofertilizers for okra cultivation improve okra productivity. Growth, phenological and yield parameters were evaluated, and the best performances in plant height (39.87 cm), number of leaves (09) and collar diameter (12.89 mm) were observed with neem cake towards the end of the production cycle. Plants treated with rabbit urine showed early floral induction and early flowering at 44 DAS and 47 DAS respectively. The best yield in average number of fruits (20,000 fruits/ha) and fruit mass (4.08 t/ha) was obtained with neem cake. It would be interesting to continue this research with varied doses of biofertilizers, increase the number of okra varieties for better diversification of the species, know the physicochemical constitution of the soil and the biofertilizers used in order to better assess the contributions.

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